

BrainViz: A Scientific Gateway for Deploying AI Methods to be used as a Clinical Decision Support System for Treatment in Brain Disorders.

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ABSTRACT

We present BrainViz, novel scientific gateway (SG) designed for psychiatry researchers to access artificial intelligence (AI) methods and explore options for treatment and characterization of various phases of disease. Our initial implementation of BrainViz provides access to (1) analysis tools, (2) visualization tools, (3) collaboration capabilities, (4) cluster computing, and (5) a data repository. We have implemented BrainViz as a scalable web application built using the Python Django[1] framework within Amazon Web Services (AWS) with a HIPAA-compliant architecture[2]. Amazon Relational Database Service[3] (RDS), a scalable, serverless database, is used for the back end. The data repository storage is configured using S3 with backups of the repository synchronized to a separate Glacier storage tier within AWS. The front-end website is hosted at brainviz.net, introducing this SG to the community. A user may (1) create an account; (2) manage contact information, affiliation, and password; (3) learn about and join a collaborative community; (4) upload community datasets; (5) test a compliant dataset using an existing AI model; (6) visualize the results of the application of the model; (7) share data derivatives with the community.

In our current implementation, we have deployed BrainViz to provide a SG for a mood disorder project that assesses a difficult-to-diagnose bipolar or major depression patient and predicts the better medication class. In past work by our team, we trained and implemented an AI model to predict future medication class performance, either anti-depressants (AD) or mood stabilizers (MS) using a resting-state functional magnetic resonance (rs-fMR) scan and future positive medication response as inputs[4]. A user may upload a novel scan to the SG. We will provide a guide to the user on the suggested scanning parameters. In this mood disorder project, BrainViz will do the following steps: (1) anonymize the dataset and discard any raw data initially submitted; (2) convert the dataset into the BIDS[5] format; (3) preprocess the rs-fMR; (4) perform a spatially constrained independent component analysis using the NeuroMark template[6]; (5) perform a prediction of medication response; (6) generate a report of the classification summary.

Figure 1 shows an example report that can be visualized and used to guide a clinical decision for treatment.

BrainViz users may interact with other community members for a given project and access relevant documentation and resources, including a forum. Further, BrainViz users may share anonymized or preprocessed data with other users. This will expand the network of users engaged in mood disorders research to help further validate and generalize this prediction model. Our hope is to establish a diverse collection of scanners, sites, and subjects within our training, testing, and validation samples for the AI model. Further, we will use this SG to prepare for clinical trials where the safety and efficacy of using the BrainViz medication classifier as a clinical decision support system will be evaluated[7]. Finally, other projects using MRI and phenotype information for predicting treatment options, disease severity, or disease progression will be explored using BrainViz, expanding its utility across other psychiatric and neurological disorders.

Figure 1: Sample BrainViz report

Keywords— Precision Medicine; MRI; Mental Health; Brain

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